

COMPARISON OF DAMAGE BEHAVIOUR IN STRUCTURES REINFORCED BY KNITTED AND WOVEN TEXTILE FABRICS

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SUMMARY: In many applications, composite materials are damaged by static deflections or by deflections due to impacts at low energy. Damage tolerance of glass/epoxy weft knitted textile fabric-reinforced sandwich and monolithic samples is studied in comparison with woven textile fabrics. In the first part it is shown that the knitted fabric-reinforced sandwich sheets provide greater resistance to the damage evolution than the woven sheets in case of sheets of the same thickness. Whereas, in case of sheets displaying the same number of plies a thickness effect appears. In the second part the efficiency of knitted fabrics is analysed by considering deflections through impacts on monolithic samples of the same thickness and on samples displaying the same number of plies. Damage evolutions versus the number of impacts are established for knitted and woven fabric-reinforced monolithic samples.

KEYWORDS: Knitted fabric reinforcements, woven fabric reinforcements, damage measurement, three-point bending, low energy impact deflection.

INTRODUCTION

For their light weight, high bending stiffness and strength, composite materials are used in wide industrial applications such as aeronautic and naval industries. The major textile forming techniques for composing reinforcements are weaving, providing significant damage tolerance. However, knitted textile fabrics can be formed into a three dimensional shape in a simple deepdraw-like production shape [1] and are therefore attractive reinforcement materials. Elastic properties of knitted fabric-reinforced composites have been investigated elsewhere [2]. Yet, their damage tolerance is unfortunately unknown.

Thus, tests were conducted in order to compare damaging processes of monolithic and sandwich samples reinforced by knitted and woven fabrics. Damage by three-point bending tests and by deflections through impacts at low energy were analysed. Knitted and woven fabric reinforcements were chosen with approximately the same specific gravity of 165 g/m².

MATERIALS USED

The knitted fabric used is a single jersey. Its structure is described in Fig.1. In order to have a valid reference for the damage tolerance of the knitted fabric-composites, a woven fabric-composite is manufactured as well.

Fig. 1: Knitted fabric structure.

In the first part sandwich structures with a lightweight foam core (80 kg/m^3), 10 mm thick, are tested. The sheets are stratified with epoxy resin using 1, 2 or 3 knitted or woven glass ply-sheets. Sandwich samples are noted type A, B, C, D or E and their composite skins are fabricated as is described below in Table 1. The assembly consisting of an equal number of fabric-plyes on either side is obtained by contact moulding. The product is a symmetric sandwich panel with excellent bonding between composite skin and resin core.

Table 1: Sandwich structures.

Type	core	sheets	sheet thickness
A	foam Airex	epoxy resin, one knitted fabric-ply	0.7 mm
B	foam Airex	epoxy resin, two knitted fabric-plyes	1.5 mm
C	foam Airex	epoxy resin, one woven fabric-ply	0.2 mm
D	foam Airex	epoxy resin, two woven fabric-plyes	0.4 mm
E	foam Airex	epoxy resin, three woven fabric-plyes	0.7 mm

In the second part parallelepipedical notched samples of stratified glass epoxy resin, using the two types of reinforcements are damaged. They are stratified under vacuum at room temperature for 4 hours and then post cured at 100°C for 2 hours. The thickness of monolithic specimens is 3 and 7 mm, their dimensions are $80 * 15 \text{ mm}$.

Owing to their structure knitted textiles are thicker than woven textiles. The effects of reinforcement types and thickness are therefore discussed further. For the sandwich structures, damage is generated by successive three-point bending deflections of 3 mm. For the monolithic structures a Charpy hammer is used to conduct deflections through impacts at low energy.

THREE-POINT BENDING TESTS

Two kinds of experiments are conducted in order to compare damaging of sandwiches with knitted or woven sheets: tests on sandwich samples with sheets of the same thickness, tests on sandwich samples with sheets displaying the same number of plies. Specimens dimensions are: 180*30 mm. Knitted fabric-reinforced composites exhibit various mechanical properties in the wale and course directions. Elastic modulus is better in the wale direction [2], thus the knitted fabric-reinforced samples are tested only in the wale direction. At least five specimens are tested for each sandwich or monolithic sample.

Tests procedure

Three-point bending tests are performed with an hydraulic machine at room temperature. The length between the outer points is 100 mm. A vertical load P is applied in the middle of the sample. The evolution of $P=f(w)$, the load P versus the deflection w at the middle of the sample, is recorded. The load increases from 0 to 130 N and the loading speed is of about 0.2 mm/s. Up to a deflection of 0.5 mm, the behaviour is linear. The stiffness is determined by the slope of $P=f(w)$ and is linked to the non damage sheet Young modulus. Each sample from type A, B, C, D or E is loaded up to a given deflection of 3 mm and then unloaded to zero: this loading and unloading procedure represents one damaging cycle. A maximum number of cycles can be performed on each type of sandwich. At this number, damage is extensive and the slope of $P=f(w)$ is non linear. Damage is induced by successive deflections. Quantification of damaging is established by using the concept of Rabotnov and Kachanov [3]. Damage value D^* is a function of the stiffness decrease and defined as follows by:

$$D^*=1-K^*/K \quad (1)$$

K^* is the stiffness of the damaged sample measured after each cycle. K is the stiffness of the non-damaged sample. Sandwich samples with sheets of the same thickness and sandwiches with sheets displaying the same number of plies are tested.

Sheet thickness influence

For the same thickness, woven sheets display three plies (E) whereas knitted sheets display only one ply (A), Table 1. The evolution of damage value versus N , the number of cycles, is shown in Fig.2.

It appears that knitted fabric-reinforced sheet (A) is more resistant to bending deflections than woven fabric-reinforced sheet (E). Damage values increase from 0.15 to 0.35 for the woven sheet and from 0.05 to 0.3 for the knitted sheet. Moreover, the number of cycles N leading to extensive damage is different: it is equal to 30 for knitted sheets as opposed to 20 for the woven sheets.

Fig. 2: Damage versus the number of deflections, types (A) and (E).

Influence of the number of plies

Damage value, Fig.3, is twice as low for sandwiches with one knitted-ply-sheets (A) when compared to the damage of sandwiches with one woven-ply-sheets (C). On the other hand, Fig.4, the evolution of the damage is twice as high and faster for sandwiches with two knitted-ply-sheets (B) compared to that of sandwiches with two woven-ply-sheets (D). After 25 bending deflections, the damage value is of 0.65 for the woven sheets and only of 0.3 for the knitted sheets. At this state, a thickness effect appears: knitted fabric-reinforced sheets (B) are thick and damage process is due to local punching occurring during the three-point bending tests. This phenomenon has been described in details elsewhere [4]. The thin knitted fabric-reinforced sandwich sheets display a better damage tolerance than the woven fabric-reinforced sheets.

Fig. 3: Damage versus the number of deflections, one knitted and woven ply.

Fig. 4: Damage versus the number of deflections, two knitted and woven plies.

DEFLECTIONS BY MEANS OF IMPACT TESTS

For composite materials effects of the deflections due to impacts are not always well known. Damage is characterised by the progressive evolution of the crack propagation and the delamination inside the composite materials and is thereby difficult to quantify. Experiments were conducted on knitted and woven fabric-reinforced monolithic specimens. The thickness of the knitted textiles is 2 to 3 times greater than that of the woven textiles: thus, tests were run on samples of the same thickness and on samples displaying the same number of plies. Evolution of damage versus the impact energy (one only impact) and evolution of damage versus the number of successive impacts (for a given energy) are analysed.

Test procedure

Dimensions of notched specimens are 80*15 mm. Each ply is stratified using epoxy resin. A modified Charpy hammer is used in order to conduct experiments. Incident impact energies are generated in the range from 1 to 12 Joules (incident speed from 0.45 m/s to 1.1 m/s) by changing the drop height. Incident energy level is chosen in order to avoid rupture at the first impact. Incident energy is defined as follows:

$$E_{inc} = m \cdot g \cdot L \cdot (1 - \cos\theta) \quad (2)$$

where m is the weight of the impactor, L is the length of the pendulum, and θ is the angle between the vertical direction and the pendulum axe, Fig.5.

Fig. 5: The impact test.

The quantification of the damage evolution is also established by using the concept of Rabotnov and Kachanov [3]. The damage value D^* is a function of the stiffness modulus decrease and defined as follows:

$$D^* = 1 - E^*/E \tag{3}$$

where E^* is the stiffness of the damaged sample measured after each cycle and E is the stiffness of the non-damaged sample. Stiffnesses are measured by a three point-bending test.

Results, single impact test for samples of the same thickness

Parallelepipedical samples of stratified glass/epoxy are tested displaying 22 knitted fabric-reinforced plies and 64 woven fabric-reinforced plies. The thickness is equal for both and is about 7 mm. Evolution of the damage D^* versus the energy level for knitted and woven fabric-reinforced specimens is shown , Fig.6.

Fig. 6: Damage value versus the impact energy level, knitted and woven fabric-reinforced specimens, same thickness.

In the case of a single impact, a threshold value of incident energy corresponding to the beginning of the damage process is pointed out. The threshold value is about 4J for the woven fabric-reinforced samples and 1.3 J for the knitted fabric-reinforced samples. This threshold value is 3 times lower in case of knitted fabrics: the rate of reinforcements is also 3 times lower (22 knitted plies/ 64 woven plies). For a given rate of reinforcements, damage tolerance appears similar.

Results, successive impacts on samples of the same thickness

The thickness of the knitted and woven fabric-reinforced samples is 7 mm. Impact tests are conducted in a range from 1.9 J to 2.8 J for knitted fabric-reinforced samples and in a range from 5.9 J to 12 J for woven fabric-reinforced samples. Energy ranges are different : for each type of reinforcement the impact energy is necessary greater than the threshold damaging value and lower than the rupture value (for only one impact). Thereby, in order to compare the two types of reinforcements damage values D^* are plotted versus the ratio n/N_{max} . $D^* = f(n/N_{max})$ as shown on Fig.7 for knitted samples (all energy levels) and on Fig.8 for woven samples (all energy levels). N_{max} is the number of impacts leading to rupture.

Fig. 7: $D^*=f(n/N_{max})$, knitted fabric-reinforced samples, 3 impact energies.

Fig. 8: $D^*=f(n/N_{max})$, woven fabric-reinforced samples, 4 impact energies.

Whatever the impact energy level from 1.9 J to 2.8 J for the knitted fabric-reinforced samples, Fig.7, and from 5.9 J to 12 J for the woven fabric-reinforced samples, Fig.8, the damage evolutions versus the ration n/N_{max} are similar. These evolutions fit with the theoretical damage model [5] defined as follows and shown Fig.9:

$$D^* = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{n}{N_{max}}\right)^{\frac{1}{1+a}} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 9: Schematic diagram $D^*=f(n/N_{max})$.

In case of knitted reinforcements $a=3.65$ whereas $a=0$ for the woven reinforcements and the evolution is linear. Results emphasise that the knitted fabric-reinforced samples display a better damage tolerance to bending deflections through impacts. Damage values obtained for knitted reinforcements at a given n/N_{max} are always lower than that obtained for woven ones.

Samples of the same number of plies

Knitted and woven fabric-reinforced 22 ply-samples are tested under three incident energy levels in a same range of 1.9 J to 2.8 J. The thickness of the knitted structure is 7 mm and that of the woven structure is 2.8 mm. Samples are damaged by successive impacts. Evolution $D^*=f(n/N_{max})$ is similar for the two types of reinforced samples, Fig.10. However for a given impact energy the critical number of impacts N_{max} is twice greater for knitted fabric-reinforced samples than for the woven ones, Table 2.

Fig. 10: $D^*=f(n/N_{max})$, samples with the same number of plies.

Table 2: Comparison of N_{max} for knitted and woven fabric-reinforced samples.

E_{inc} (J)	N_{max} knitted fabrics	N_{max} woven fabrics
1.9	16	8
2.3	6	3
2.8	4	2

CONCLUSION

An experimental study has been performed in order to evaluate the mechanical performances of knitted and woven composites and obtain a better understanding of the factors influencing the damaging properties of these materials.

Thin knitted sheet-reinforced sandwiches provide better resistance to bending deflections. If sheets are thick a local punching phenomenon occurs, independent of the deflection process.

A threshold value of impact energy corresponding to the beginning of the damage process is shown in the case of single impact on knitted fabric and woven fabric-reinforced monolithic samples. This threshold value appears linked with the reinforcements rate.

For successive impacts damage tolerance of knitted fabric-reinforced samples appears also better in terms of the damage law $D^*=f(n/N_{max})$ for samples of the same thickness and by analysing the critical number N_{max} for samples displaying the same number of plies.

As shown elsewhere for their elastic properties sandwich and monolithic structures with knitted fibre reinforcement exhibit high potential with regard to damage tolerance.

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